

Motion Planning in Crowds: Proxemics as a Base for a Socially Acceptable Behaviour

A. Antonucci, P. Bevilacqua and L. Palopoli
Dep. of Information Engineering and Computer Science
University of Trento, Trento, Italy

M. Boldrer and D. Fontanelli
Dep. of Industrial Engineering
University of Trento, Trento, Italy

I. EXTENDED ABSTRACT

When referred to robots, the word intelligence has several facets. If a robot is required to operate in full autonomy, it needs a correct understanding of its environment, of the different spaces that compose it and of their topology; it also needs to detect the different entities that are usually disseminated in the environment, to classify each of them and identify their role in relation to the robot's mission. An entity of a peculiar kind are human beings. Humans can be simply an hindrance to the robot's mission, or can be active actors in its execution (e.g., in Cobot application [1] or in shared authority approaches [2] there is a close partnership between humans and robots).

Let us now restrict the focus to a specific problem: navigation of an autonomous mobile robot across promiscuous areas, shared with human beings. In cases like this, the actions of a robot are socially acceptable insofar as they reflect the behaviours that a human would generate in similar conditions. The Anthropologist Edward C. Hall first coined the term "proxemics" in order to describe how humans use the interpersonal space and how they establish non-verbal communication channels tightly related to their interpersonal distance [3]. Hall has identified four zones where thresholds are crossed and behaviours differ: 1. Intimate space (below 450 mm apart), 2. Personal space (450 mm to 1.2 m apart), 3. Social Space (2 m to 3.6 m apart) and 4. Public space (3.6 m to 7.6 m apart). The Intimate space should never be violated except for limited circumstances (e.g., athletes tackling each other, lovers, or parent/children pairs). The Personal space allows for rather intense social interactions (e.g., holding one's hand, or engaging with friends in face-to-face informal discussions), while the Social space is reserved to more formal interactions (e.g., business transactions). Finally, the Public space is used for interaction with groups (e.g., a speech, a lecture). In this paper, we propose a cognitive architecture to manage social interactions in shared spaces closely inspired to the principle of proxemics.

Our proposal identifies four different nested layers. Layer 1, dubbed *Emergency reaction layer*, controls the action of the robot when it comes within the Intimate space of a person. With the exception of specific situation (i.e., a collaborative task demanding tight human/robot interaction), the most plausible reaction (perhaps the only one available) is to stop until the person moves away. Layer 2 is called *Reflexive reaction layer* and it becomes active when the robot is approaching the personal space of a person. In this situation, the robot promptly seeks an evasive manoeuvre that prevents its entering into the

Intimate space of the person without forcing a stop. Layer 3 is defined as the *Deliberate reaction layer*: the robot is in an area between the Social space and the Personal space; it could observe the trajectory followed by the person for some time and it can make sensible predictions on its future evolution and use them to decide a path that complies with the social rules and optimises at the same time some metrics of interest (e.g. jerk, energy consumption, comfort for the user if the robot is a walker or an automated wheelchair). Finally, Layer 4 is what we call *Interactive reaction layer*. The layer is active in an area between the far end of the Social space and the Public space. The assumption is that the robot has the person in full sight for some time. It could observe her/his gestures and interpret the body language collecting hints on the most likely decision of the person in the near-future.

Layer 1 usually falls within the responsibility of the robot makers and relies on classic emergency stops. In this paper, we will report some results related to Layer 2 and to Layer 3 and present the ongoing work on Layer 4.

Reflexive reactions. Reflexive reactions are taken under the assumption that the robot is relatively close to a human (between 1 and 2 metres apart) and that it possesses a small amount of reliable information (e.g., the human's position and pose and his/her current speed). In this case, the use of potential fields seems an appropriate choice to generate a controlled reactive behaviour, which, however, have known limitations, the most important being the presence of local minima that could prevent the progress of the robot. For this reason, potential fields have been complemented by the use of limit cycles generated by vortex fields [4], [5]. The problem with this approach is that it generates trajectories that are either non-optimal (i.e., the total deviation before the trajectory joins into its original path is very long) or quite "jerky" and socially unacceptable (i.e, they violate the intimate space of the person). Taking inspiration from the limit cycle approach, we have identified a shape for the limit cycle that allows us to keep in check the total deviation from the initial plan, while guaranteeing a sufficient smoothness of the generated trajectory and a minimum distance from the person (see Figure 1). This solution is immediate (it does not require costly computation), and it generates "reflexive" deviations that are heuristically similar to the ones typically followed by a person in these circumstances.

Deliberate reactions. The basic idea behind deliberate reaction is that we have more time to take our decision and more data to rely on. After sensors detect the human for some time they are able to extract more information on his/her

Fig. 1. Deviation in the path using the limit cycle approach.

Fig. 2. Trajectory generated by a probabilistic reactive planner.

current state and can use a predictive model to make informed guesses on its evolution on the near future. The prediction on the future position is made using the Headed Social Force Model (HFSM) [6]. The HFSM combines two different ideas: modeling the motion of a human as a body acted upon by a number of “social” forces (both repulsive and attractive), restricting the possible motion of the human to nonholonomic dynamics [7]. This idea can be exploited as follows [8]. When the robot stays in front of the person, it generates all her possible trajectories using the HFSM, randomising its free parameters and approximating them with mathematically tractable curves (clothoids). Each curve is associated with a probability that it will be taken. The planning algorithm selects several alternative paths and, for each, it computes a probability that will generate a collision. At the end, the alternative with a probability of accident below an acceptable bound that minimises the deviation from the path is selected. In Figure 2 we report the trajectory generated by the algorithm (in green) in a real experiment while the red curves represent the trajectories followed by two humans in the scene. The solution is based on the idea of modeling the human choice through some probability distribution, of propagating the choice ahead and on making a choice based on probabilistic reasoning. The result is arguably smoother and more effective than a simple reflexive reaction. There is an obvious price to pay in terms of computational resources required, but more importantly the approach has a considerable limitation: the human is always treated as a non-cooperative entity that makes his/her choices ignoring the presence of the robot. Certainly, closed loop corrections are possible (the loop rate remains perfectly acceptable), but the efficiency is still far from optimal.

Interactive reactions. It belongs to everyone’s experience that people exchange non verbal messages using the language of their body when they meet in shared spaces [9]. Eye-to-eye contact, body language, posture and hand gestures are examples of alternative ways to verbal communications whereby people can express their feelings (e.g., “I am scared”), situation awareness (e.g., “I have seen you”) or even reach a

quick mutual agreement (e.g., “ok, I go right and you go left”). Understanding in advance what a person wants to do through the clues transmitted by her body can be key to a more effective negotiation of shared spaces. We have just started to explore this possibility. Specifically, we are considering an application that extracts the skeleton of a person. In fact, back in the ’70s, [10] showed that the perception of the human actions was associable with the geometric distribution of bodies, and therefore with the skeleton and the joints that compose it. Observing the time series of the posture of head, shoulders and upper limbs enables the identification of a number of “predictors” for the future actions of the person well before they become manifest in the path she takes. These predictors can be used in a Bayesian filtering scheme to derive a better assessment of the probability associated with the curves the person can take. This marks a very strong difference from the probabilistic scheme used in the Deliberate reaction layer, where the probability is uniformly distributed across all the curves that the HFSM generates. The improved prediction of the future motion of the person will lead the robot to much more “natural” and consistent choices on its own path, with a radical improvement of the robot’s social skills.

A future and even more transformative change could be to establish a real non-verbal communication channel. In this case, after an initial prediction on the human’s motion, the robot could take a tentative decision in its turn, communicate it non-verbally to the person and evaluate her reactions. After a few iterations of this kind an agreement is reached between person and robot taking the smoothness of the interaction to its extreme limit.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Peshkin, J. Colgate, W. Wannasuphprasit, C. Moore, R. Gillespie, and P. Akella, “Cobot architecture,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 377–390, 2001.
- [2] M. Andreetto, S. Divan, F. Ferrari, D. Fontanelli, L. Palopoli, and F. Zenatti, “Simulating passivity for Robotic Walkers via Authority-Sharing,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1306–1313, April 2018.
- [3] E. T. Hall, “A system for the notation of proxemic behavior 1,” *American anthropologist*, vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 1003–1026, 1963.
- [4] D.-H. Kim and J.-H. Kim, “A real-time limit-cycle navigation method for fast mobile robots and its application to robot soccer,” *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 17–30, 2003.
- [5] L. Adouane, “Orbital obstacle avoidance algorithm for reliable and on-line mobile robot navigation,” in *9th Conference on Autonomous Robot Systems and Competitions*, 2009.
- [6] F. Farina, D. Fontanelli, A. Garulli, A. Giannitrapani, and D. Praticchizzo, “Walking ahead: The headed social force model,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–23, 01 2017.
- [7] G. Archavaleta, J.-P. Laumond, H. Hicheur, and A. Berthoz, “On the nonholonomic nature of human locomotion,” *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 25, no. 1-2, pp. 25–35, 2008.
- [8] P. Bevilacqua, M. Frego, D. Fontanelli, and L. Palopoli, “Reactive planning for assistive robots,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1276–1283, April 2018.
- [9] A. Antonucci and D. Fontanelli, “Towards a Predictive Behavioural Model for Service Robots in Shared Environments,” in *IEEE Workshop on Advanced Robotics and its Social Impacts*. Genova, Italy: IEEE, September 2018, pp. 9–14.
- [10] G. Johansson, “Visual perception of biological motion and a model for its analysis,” *Perception & psychophysics*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 201–211, 1973.